

Research Software Engineering in the N8

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Research Software Engineers in the N8

The N8 Centre of Excellence in Computationally Intensive Research (N8 CIR) has, from its beginnings, acknowledged the crucial role that Research Software Engineers (RSEs) have to play in computational research. In order to raise the profile of RSEs, build a network of RSEs and RSE leaders, as well as foster the relationships between RSEs and researchers, a dedicated RSE Theme Leader has been appointed. This role has been fulfilled by Kirsty Pringle from 2018 until 2020, and has been taken over by Marion Weinzierl in 2020.

Information on N8 CIR [RSE groups](#), a (not exhaustive) [directory of RSEs](#) in N8 CIR and their skills, and [RSE case studies](#) can be found on our [website](#).

The N8 CIR Tier-2 supercomputer [Bede](#) has a dedicated team of [Bede RSEs](#) in the Bede Support group, who support researchers to port their code to the machine and make the most of its specialised architecture. The N8 CIR RSE Theme Leader is co-leading the Bede Support group, as well as chairing the Bede User Group.

N8 CIR has close connections to the [Society of Research Software Engineering](#), and is currently considering becoming an official collaborator of the [Software Sustainability Institute](#). We have also [recently become a chapter of Women in High Performance Computing \(WHPC\)](#).

Research Software Engineering Groups

Recently, universities across the UK (and, in fact, across the globe) have started to establish central RSE groups who offer software engineering support and collaboration to researchers in all departments of their university.

The following RSE groups exist in the N8 (source:

<https://n8cir.org.uk/supporting-research/rse/research-software-engineering-groups/>):

Durham University

- **Group Name** – Advanced Research Computing
- **Group Leader** – Ed-Ruck Keene
- **Contact e-mail** – arc@durham.ac.uk

This is a central Research Software Engineering group with 4 RSEs.

Lancaster University

- **Group Name** – RSE Lancaster
- **Group Leader** – Robin Long
- **Contact e-mail** – r.long@lancaster.ac.uk

This is a newly-formed central group, currently comprising one RSE.

Newcastle University

- **Group Name** – RSE Newcastle
- **Group Leader** – Mark Turner
- **Contact e-mail** – rseteam@ncl.ac.uk

This is a central Research Software Engineering group with 14 RSEs.

University of Leeds

- **Group Name** – Research Computing
- **Group Leader** – Martin Callaghan
- **Contact e-mail** – m.callaghan@leeds.ac.uk

A central (core-funded) RSE group with six RSEs and a further 3 appointments at various stages of recruitment (as of 2021-09-29)

- **Group Name** – CEMAC
- **Group Leader** – Mark Richardson
- **Contact e-mail** – m.g.richardson@leeds.ac.uk

This is a domain-specific Research Software Engineering group with 6 RSEs. The team is based in the School of Earth and the Environment and specialise in environmental modelling and computation. Team members are not formally hired as RSEs (see section on embedded RSEs), but considered post-doctoral researchers and are funded by being named on grants.

University of Liverpool

- **Group Name** – Research Computing Group
- **Group Leader** – Jake Gannon
- **Contact e-mail** – jakeg@liverpool.ac.uk

This central group is at an early stage of development and has very limited RSE capacity available to work on projects. However, Jake Gannon is keen to hear from researchers wishing to work with RSEs to help inform how the team develops.

University of Manchester

- **Group Name** – RSE Team within Research IT
- **Group Leader** – Robert Haines
- **Contact e-mail** – robert.haines@manchester.ac.uk

This central group is the largest in the N8 with 24 RSEs.

- **Group Name:** Digital Health Software
- **Group Leader:** Matt Machin
- **Contact e-mail:** matthew.machin@manchester.ac.uk

Digital Health Software is an embedded RSE team based in the Centre for Health Informatics. The team specialises in the development of apps, databases and web-based clinician interfaces for research into a wide range of different health conditions, including multiple co-morbidities:

<https://sites.manchester.ac.uk/digital-health-software/>

University of Sheffield

- **Group Name** – RSE Sheffield
- **Group Leader** – Paul Richmond
- **Contact e-mail** – rse@sheffield.ac.uk

This is a Research Software Engineering group with 10 RSEs. It is embedded in computer science, but provides support across the university.

- **Group Name** – Digital Humanities Institute
- **Group Leader** – Michael Pidd
- **Contact e-mail** – m.pidd@sheffield.ac.uk

Established in 1994, the DHI is the UK's leading centre for digital humanities and technology R&D in the arts, humanities and cultural heritage domains. The DHI is a team of RSEs, project managers and researchers. We collaborate on UKRI projects. We have delivered more than 120 projects and we host 70+ public websites and information services. See: <http://www.dhi.ac.uk>

University of York

- **Group Name** – Research and High Performance Support Team
- **Group Leader** – Emma Barnes
- **Contact e-mail** – emma.barnes@york.ac.uk

This is a central Research Software Engineering Group with 3 RSEs.

- **Group Name** – Condensed Matter Dynamics
- **Group Leaders** – Matt Probert and Phil Hasnip
- **Contact e-mail** – peter.byrne@york.ac.uk

This domain-specific Research Software Engineering Group has 2 RSEs and is based in the Department of Physics.

Embedded RSEs

In contrast to RSEs in central groups, who can work in various research groups at varying levels of involvement and time commitment, embedded RSEs are directly employed by a research group/academic. While some university departments explicitly specify a post as an RSE role (though sometimes with slightly varying names), they are often employed as post-docs, research assistants, or even PhD candidates.

For these RSEs, the right balance between research commitments and software engineering best practices can often be even harder to achieve, as they are fully embedded in a research environment. On the other hand, they are better placed than central RSEs to continue on a research or academic career.

Survey on Career and Training for RSEs in the N8

An informal survey was contacted over the mailing list of the RSE leaders in N8 CIR. The aim was to get a rough overview of the status quo of career pathways and training opportunities for RSE in the N8. The full questions and answers are given below.

Answers by

- Durham: Marion Weinzierl
- Lancaster: Robin Long
- Leeds: Mark Richardson; Martin Callaghan
- Liverpool: Jake Gannon
- Manchester: Rob Haines
- Newcastle: Mark Turner
- Sheffield: Paul Richmond
- York: Emma Barnes

Are the RSEs in your group (officially) professional support staff, research staff, academic staff, or something else?

University	Answer
Durham	The central ARC RSE group is classed as professional support.
Lancaster	RSEs are classified as research staff most of the time, but this is not a hard rule.
Leeds	My team is a group of 4 post-docs and 1 equivalent to post-doc by experience, and myself a post-doc; my role is to manage all the project work that we attract and assign it to the members of my team; their PhD puts them on the research staff roster but they are usually named on funded projects as fractions of effort. The central RSE team are <i>officially</i> professional services staff.
Liverpool	Could probably make a case for all of the above
Manchester	The RSEs in the UoM central pool are part of Research IT in IT Services, so are Professional Staff.
Newcastle	They're classed as technical staff, which is a group within the professional support family
Sheffield	Employed on RSE job description which can be either research/technical pathway.
York	We have two provided centrally and others that are funded by research groups.

What kind of (official) career path exists for RSE at your institution, and what does that mean in terms of grades? (e.g. Junior RSE - grade 6, RSE - grade 7, Senior RSE - grade 8, RSE leader - grade 9)

University	Answer
Durham	No official career path, we currently have (“standard”) RSEs and one Head of RSE. Further grades are in work.
Lancaster	None, it follows the researcher path
Leeds	<p>There is no publicised RSE career path at Leeds. The formal “RSE team” at Leeds is a subset of Central IT formed from the HPC system support team, they attend to the whole of the institute but rarely work with my school other than direct HPC support. My team will follow the academic researcher scale. NOTE: grade 7 at Leeds might not mean the same as grade 7 at the other institutes (I know for a fact that Reading is numerically one lower than Leeds).</p> <p>In the central team, RSEs are appointed at UoL Grade 7. We have a modern apprentice/ training grade at G6 (that’ll be the next appointment) and are developing a promotion pathway to G8. Made a little more challenging as RSEs aren’t academic posts nor understood fully by IT Services.</p>
Liverpool	No specific career path for RSEs it just follows either an academic or PS path. There is work underway to create a 3 rd pathway for RSE type roles.
Manchester	We have 3 RSE job descriptions at grades 5, 6, and 7. Head of RSE is grade 8. I think UoM grade numbers are different from other places. For reference, at UoM grade 6 is PDRA, grade 7 is Lecturer, grade 8 is Senior Lecturer/Reader and grade 9 is Professor.
Newcastle	Newcastle’s grades are lettered E – Junior F – Standard G – Senior H – Leader
Sheffield	RSE (G7 - postdoc level) and Senior RSE (G8 - Lecturer level), potential to progress to G9/10 through the academic careers pathway.
York	The career path needs some work in York. This is something I am looking into and hoping to improve but will need buy-in from HR and University leaders.

What kind of training is available for your RSEs at your university, in particular for Professional Development (non-technical)? The same as for academics and researchers, the same as for professional support staff, both, other?

University	Answer
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Durham	DCAD offers staff training centrally, but some of it is only for research/academic staff (and others just for PS staff). I talked to them, though, and they offered to make any training available to the RSEs that seems relevant.
Lancaster	Both
Leeds	All training for my team is as per individual requirement and the Head of School will approve that expenditure; actually it seems they are reluctant to do more than the typical learning on the job background reading. Even when I ask them to attend courses. The University has a “people development” group that provides a broad spectrum of training and all are welcome to enroll.
Liverpool	Training is available to all types and ranges from centrally provided training from HR and the IT department, local training within faculties, training align to a specific project and access to LinkedIn Learning.
Manchester	This is all done at an institutional level so the same sorts of things are available to all.
Newcastle	Staff can access most training whatever grade or job family they’re in with some exceptions. However, those exceptions make sense, it’s things like only being able to access training on teaching if you’re in a teaching role. This is usually to limit interest due to demand, they want to prioritise people who really need it.
Sheffield	Same
York	There is no official training. It also depends on what they are doing and where they sit. All RSEs can attend courses at the university that may be relevant to their area of work. If they are centrally funded training is generally 1:1 or they can attend a central course that may be relevant.

Is there an official RSE job description for embedded RSEs in departments at your institution?

University	Answer
Durham	The Physics department has (at least one) official embedded RSE with that job title in a researcher-developer-type role, and other RSE-type roles with slightly different job titles.
Lancaster	No.
Leeds	There has not been a public job description of RSE other than those on the “research computing team” (HPC support staff) when central IT started recruiting in 2019. When we advertise for personnel my director (an academic) will create a job description and the HR staff will check and approve it. Central HR have agreed a standard HERA-type JD for a G7 RSE which it is expected that all RSE job titles (including embedded) would follow.
Liverpool	Not an official one but there is variation in use, normally created by the recruiting manager.

Manchester	As far as I am aware the only official “HERAed” RSE job description is ours in IT Services, and I don’t think anyone else uses it.
Newcastle	For central RSEs yes, for embedded RSEs sometimes. It’s getting better but some are still listed as things like Software Specialist or Research Programmer.
Sheffield	Yes, but not a pathway. This follows the academic career pathway. There are also people who identify as RSEs on technical contracts in professional services.
York	There is a job description that is used.

A number of RSEs are qualified [Software Carpentry](#) trainers. This qualification requires an [institutional membership](#). It was considered to acquire such a membership for N8 CIR, but as some N8 universities already are Software Carpentry members, it was decided against.

For RSEs that provide a significant number of hours of teaching per year there should be (and definitely is, for example, in Durham and Sheffield) the possibility to take part in programs that lead to an [Associate Fellowship of the Higher Education Academy \(AFHEA\)](#). For those who are interested, it is worthwhile contacting the appropriate people at the respective university and inquire about those programs.

Funding for Research Software Engineering

While RSEs can be costed into research grants as Co-Is, named researchers, or unnamed RSE effort, there is an increasing number of calls for specific Research Software Engineering projects. In the past, EPSRC offered dedicated [RSE Fellowships](#) which, however, have been discontinued after the 2020 round. Instead, RSEs are encouraged to apply to the [Open Fellowships](#).

In 2021, EPSRC also had a [Software for Research Communities](#) call, which states “We note the significant contribution of staff such as research software engineers (RSEs) to interdisciplinary computational projects, and support the recognition of their vital contributions to research outcomes. We encourage applicants to acknowledge and cost RSEs on research grant applications where appropriate.”. In addition, there is the [Support the Development of Research Software Engineering](#) call (also called “Future of RSE” call) for developing RSE education and training, mainly focussed on High Performance Computing (in the realm of the ExCALIBUR programme).

The [ExCALIBUR](#) programme is an ongoing EPSRC program with calls targeting high performance simulation software, which states as one of its four pillars “Investment in People - Improved RSE career development driven by professional forward-looking approach to scientific software design of simulation codes.” and has [RSE Knowledge Integration](#) as one of its themes.

Apart from EPSRC, other funding agencies are starting to see the importance of Research Software Engineering for science. For example, STFC has funded one of the fellowships of the last RSE Fellowship round.

For smaller, targeted projects to improve computational practice, the [fellowships of the Software Sustainability Institute](#) (SSI) provide 3000£ funding, as well as a network of current and former fellows. Over the past few years, several RSEs and other researchers involved in research software development in the N8 have applied for (and been awarded) SSI fellowships.

